

APPLICATION OF SPINAL ANESTHESIA FOR CESAREAN SECTION IN PREGNANT WOMAN WITH SEVERE COVID 19 PNEUMONIA - A CASE REPORT**Koritarova V.***Phd- doctor in Specialized University Hospital for Obstetric and Gynecology ,, Maichin dom'' Sofia, Bulgaria***Abstract**

Pregnancy leads to important physiological and immunological changes, which could complicate viral and bacterial infections. Many pregnant women with COVID-19 infection are asymptomatic. However among those with respiratory symptoms incidence of severe pneumonia, admission in Intensive Care Unit, need of non-invasive and invasive mechanical ventilation are higher than in other population.

Maternal respiratory failure may cause fetal distress, which requires urgent Cesarean section. Regional anesthesia is preferred, because it is considered safer than general anesthesia for mother and fetus and it exposes less medical personal to the virus. Management of pregnant women with respiratory failure, severe pneumonia, who are treated with non-invasive or invasive mechanical ventilation is a challenge for anesthesiologists.

Keywords: ARDS, CPAP, PEEP, COVID 19, FiO₂

Introduction: Pregnancy causes reduction of functional residual capacity and pulmonary compliance. In pregnant women minute ventilation and oxygen consumption are increased, their immunological response is suppressed and respiratory viruses and bacteria often causes complications. The morbidity of COVID 19 SARS in pregnant patients is almost the same as in general population. Only 32,8% of pregnant women have symptoms like temperature, shortness of breathing, dyspnea, cough, fatigue muscular pain, headache, etc. Mortality of COVID 19 SARS in pregnant patients is almost four times higher than other population-25%. [1,2,3]

According to recommendations of society of anesthesiologists` regional anesthesia for Cesarean section is safe and most effective for mother and fetus. It does not increase risk of spreading and contamination with the virus. [4]

General anesthesia in pregnant patients is considered more dangerous because of high incidence of difficult intubation, pulmonary aspiration syndrome, transfer of anesthetics and opioids through placenta to fetus and contamination of medical personal with the virus. In patient with pulmonary pathology there is risk of aggravation. [5,6]

In cases of moderate to severe COVID 19 pneumonia thrombocytopenia is observed. [7] These patients are treated with anticoagulants and we must pay attention to the time of their last intake. According to same studies in patients with severe form of COVID 19 infection is observed dysfunction of autonomic vegetative nerve system, which could lead to severe hypotension after spinal and epidural anesthesia. [8,9] In cases of Cesarean section level of spinal motor block reaches respiratory intercostal muscles and that could worsen respiratory fatigue and increase respiratory work and oxygen consumption. So in patients treated before surgery with non-invasive CPAP mask ventilation or high flow nasal cannula treatment have to continue in operating room. When patient's condition allows it is recommended use of non-rebreather reservoir bag mask with oxygen, because the devices which provide non-invasive respiratory support could

cause viral contamination of operating room. General anesthesia is applied in cases of urgency, shock, thrombocytopenia, severe pneumonia, preoperative invasive mechanical ventilation, etc. Rapid sequence induction is preferred, because it decreases frequency of pulmonary aspiration. After delivery of fetus diaphragm is decompressed, so functional residual capacity and respiratory compliance increase. Respiratory mechanics and oxygenation of patients improve.

Case report: A pregnant woman in 27 gestation week was admitted in specialized university hospital for obstetric and gynecology „Maichin dom" Sofia Bulgaria with symptoms of respiratory viral infection and uterine contractions. She does not have any other diseases. Tocolytic therapy was started, but during her hospital stay the patient complained of shortness of breathing, dyspnea, cough with sputum, fatigue and temperature. During physical examination she was subfebrile with cyanosis, tachypnea, auscultation of lungs was performed and bilateral wet and dry wheezing were heard, saturation-75-80% on room's air- symptoms of respiratory failure. Her hemodynamic was stable but sinus tachycardia until 120/min was presented. PCR test for COVID19 SARS was performed and it was positive. Arterial blood gas analysis (ABG) reveals hypoxia, hypocapnea - pH-7,43, PaO₂-45 mm Hg, PaCO₂-29 mm Hg, PaO₂/FiO₂-215. X-ray of chest was performed and it showed bilateral pulmonary diffuse interstitial and alveolar ground-glass type of infiltrations. The pregnant patient was diagnosed with severe COVID 19 pneumonia and Acute respiratory Distress Syndrome (ARDS). From laboratory tests pregnant woman was with anemia, high values of procalcitonin, ferritin, C-reactive protein (CRP), neutrophilia, lymphopenia, normal liver enzymes and hemostasis- Hb-88, Hct- 0,27, Plt-244, CRP-17,74, increased DD -dimers, procalcitonin-0,58, ALAT- 19, ASAT-21, neutrophils -80%, lymphocytes-8,6% ferritin - 220. According to same studies higher values of CRP, procalcitonin and liver enzymes indicate severe form of COVID 19 infection and they are connected with poor prognosis. [10,11,12]

Urgent cesarean section was performed, because of her critical condition and fetal distress. During her transport to operation room non-rebreather oxygen mask with reservoir bag was applied. Spinal anesthesia was chosen because of its advantages. Pregnant woman was turned in left lateral position spinal anesthesia was applied on L3-4 level with pencil point 25 G needle. Hyperbaric bupivacaine of 12,5 mg was used with morphine 0,1 mg in intrathecal space. Before spinal anesthesia about 1000 ml crystalloid were infused. The level of sensitive spinal block reached dermatome Th-5. The patient started breathing with more efforts, and tachypnea and dyspnea worsened. So adjustable pressure-limiting valve (APL) of anesthetic machine was closed at 5 mm H₂O and continuous positive airway pressure was applied on her. That improved her oxygenation and endotracheal intubation and invasive mechanical ventilation were avoided. Induced by spinal anesthesia sympathetic block decreased her arterial blood pressure and crystalloid and colloid infusions, vasopressors were used. The baby was also with respiratory distress syndrome, so she was intubated and admitted in neonatal intensive care unit. The surgery proceeded without any complications and our patient was admitted to Intensive Care Unit (ICU). There non-invasive continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) with suitable face mask was applied. It was started with positive end expiratory pressure (PEEP) 6 cm H₂O, pressure support during inspiration 10 cm H₂O, FiO₂-70%. These parameters reduced her respiratory rates, improved her respiratory work, oxygenation and ventilation. Analgo-sedation with midazolam and fentanyl was used. During the next 24 hours these parameters of non-invasive ventilation with CPAP face mask were reduced gradually. After 12 hours only PEEP 5 cm H₂O was used, and FiO₂ was decreased to 40%. Therapy with corticosteroids, anticoagulant, antibiotics was applied. ABG analysis was performed - pH-7,44, PaO₂ -159 mm Hg, PaCO₂- 33 mm Hg, saturation 98%, PaO₂/FiO₂ - 397. Her condition improved and after 2 days on CPAP mask non-invasive ventilation oxygen therapy continued with non rebreather oxygen mask with reservoir bag, which was replaced with oxygen face mask. After 7 days in ICU she was discharged.

Discussion: Physiological respiratory changes in pregnancy and suppressed immune response determine more frequent complications from viral and bacterial infections. According to same studies in population of pregnant women cases of respiratory complications like severe pneumonia- unilateral or bilateral, ARDS, which have to be treated with noninvasive or invasive mechanical ventilation are more common.[2,13,14] Comorbidities like preeclampsia, diabetes, obesity could worsen COVID 19 infection. [15] Severe pneumonia is connected with higher rate of maternal mortality-11%.

In cases of asymptomatic COVID 19 infection regional anesthesia- spinal, epidural, combination of low dose spinal and epidural anesthesia are recommended. However studies proved that these types of anesthesia increase frequency of hypotension, and that leads to application of vasopressors.

In moderate form of COVID 19 pulmonary infection regional anesthesia is also recommended, but for adequate maternal oxygenation and ventilation many patients may need support with non-invasive CPAP mask ventilation, high flow nasal cannula during surgery. [16] These devices could spread the virus and infect medical staff. Sometimes non-rebreathing oxygen mask with reservoir bag could provide adequate oxygenation. Application of non-invasive CPAP mask ventilation or high flow oxygen nasal cannula could reduce mortality and duration of ICU's stay in patients with severe COVID 19 pneumonia. [16, 17] General anesthesia in pregnant women with severe COVID 19 pneumonia, ARDS and reduced functional residual capacity could worsen their hypoxemia. General anesthesia could induce atelectasis in these patients and they more likely may require prolonged postoperative mechanical ventilation. [18] Regional anaesthesia reduces the risk of exposure of medical staff to coronavirus due to aerosol generation.[19]

Conclusion: General anesthesia in pregnant patients is connected with life-threatening conditions as difficult intubation and ventilation, pulmonary aspiration syndrome and high rate of mortality. In cases of COVID 19 severe pneumonia general anesthesia may worsen respiratory function creating atelectasis, which cause hypoxia. Regional anesthesia is considered safe for mother, fetus and medical staff.

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